

DEVELOPMENT OF SELF-EDUCATIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS AS PART OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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It is known that any activity achieves perfection only when it is regular. This applies to a special extent to mastering a foreign language (Russian as a foreign language), since in this case we are talking about teaching language and speech through the student himself. In addition, the specificity of a foreign language is that a language cannot be taught, it can only be learned, i.e. the student must show maximum activity and independence in all types of speech activity. Independent work of a student is one of the main components in the overall structure of the educational process at a university. The importance of this problem is also associated with the new role of independent work, which it acquires in connection with the transition to the competency-based education paradigm, as a result of which this form of organizing educational time becomes the leading one. Thus, self-educational competence is one of the most relevant competencies that must be developed among students in the educational process of a university. According to E.N. Fomina, self-educational competence is a personality quality that characterizes her ability for systematic, independently organized cognitive activity aimed at continuing her own education in general cultural and professional aspects [1]. Self-educational competence is formed and developed in the process of activities aimed at developing certain behavior scenarios.

Considering the independent work of students as a planned type of activity, which is carried out according to the instructions and with the methodological guidance of the teacher, it should be emphasized that the main task of the teacher is to create psychological and didactic conditions for the formation and development of self-educational competence, and thus to stimulate intellectual initiative, thinking and professional growth of future specialists.

In the system of higher professional education (as well as in the system of pre-university preparation of foreign students), the formation of self-educational competence in a foreign language (Russian as a foreign language) presupposes:

1) students' mastery of a complex of speech, language, sociocultural knowledge in a foreign (Russian as a foreign) language and various ways of

working with language material, which are the foundation of independent cognitive activity, knowledge of self-education technologies, techniques for working with reference literature (cognitive component);

2) development of “the ability to self-organize cognitive activity (selection of sources of knowledge and forms of self-education, planning, self-control)”, the ability to work with reference literature and use the capabilities of modern technologies, the ability to overcome language difficulties, the skills of independent mastery of knowledge and skills using various sources and in various forms of self-education (activity component);

3) the formation of moral and volitional qualities of the individual, activity and perseverance in mastering the language, the development of the need for language self-education based on the awareness of the personal importance of constant replenishment of knowledge (affective component) [2].

To date, certain theoretical baggage has been accumulated in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language and there is sufficient practical experience in organizing and managing students’ extracurricular independent work. However, with the traditional form of teaching, the teacher, without changing the forms of work, will not be able to achieve effective language acquisition by foreign students, and their independent work is mainly limited to studying the material presented by the teacher in class and performing exercises strictly indicated by the teacher. We believe that independent work should cover various aspects of educational work: studying and performing, theoretical and practical, thinking and external speech. It greatly contributes to the mobilization of the student’s self-organization skills and his ability to demonstrate his individual abilities. Independent work allows you to broaden your horizons by assimilating linguistic and cultural information, change your attitude towards the language you are learning in a positive way, and also develop in students the ability to study independently not only at university, but throughout your life. Particularly relevant in the process of independent work of foreign students is the development of motivation, interest in learning the Russian language, disciplines in their specialty, because It is these qualities that constitute the “internal” result of educational activity.

It is no secret that quite old people come to universities with already formed motives for learning, value orientations, interests, with their own individual psychological characteristics, which cannot be ignored in the educational process. The need for students to develop skills and abilities to work independently during the learning process is caused by the fact that many

foreign students do not have a sufficient level of work with scientific and fiction literature; some students do not have an internal psychological attitude towards the need for independent work during extracurricular time.

I.B. Akinshina believes that for students to work effectively independently, a number of conditions are necessary:

- ensuring the correct combination of volumes of classroom and independent work;
- methodologically correct organization of student work in the classroom and outside the classroom;
- providing the student with the necessary teaching materials in order to transform the process of independent work into a creative process;
- control over the organization and progress of independent work and measures to encourage the student for its high-quality implementation [3].

We believe that in the organization and management of students' independent work there is always a place for the pedagogical creativity of the teacher. The success of the organization and leadership is determined by the teacher's readiness to construct open to creativity, dynamically restructuring joint intellectual and communicative activities with students in a specific educational situation.

When organizing independent work for foreign students, you can use the following types of work:

- reading adapted and original literary texts;
- reading literature in the specialty;
- reading Russian newspapers and magazines;
- abstracting of scientific articles;
- educational Olympiads;
- test papers;
- tests;
- taking notes and performing exercises using electronic textbooks.

The main forms of control of independent work can be considered:

- oral response;
- performing tests and tests;
- scientific and practical conferences for students;
- Announcement;
- extracurricular activities.

It should also be noted that the effectiveness of students' independent work is largely determined by the presence of active methods of its control, while

control should not be an end in itself for the teacher, but, above all, become a motivating factor in the student's educational activity.

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